

MECHANICS OF CRACK ARREST IN SHORT FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITE*

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ABSTRACT

The theoretical analysis for crack arrest in short-fiber reinforced composite are presented in this paper. Both unidirectional and random orientational short fibers in the matrix are considered. Stress intensity factor and strain energy density factor are used to show the crack arresting effects.

Keywords: short-fiber reinforced composity, microcrack arrest.

1. INTRODUCTION

In comparison with the continuous fiber reinforced composites, the short-fiber reinforced composites can easily meet the demand of the macroscopical isotropic in constitution, and the automatic manufacture for short-fiber reinforced composite enables its inexpensive production. These cause the short-fiber reinforced composites to develop at a more rapid rate in recent years.

Since in short-fiber reinforced composites the short fibers tend to resist the crack propagation in the matrix, high strength and high toughness will be deserved. Taya^[1,2], Erdogan and Pacella^[3], Mori and Mara^[11], Romualdi and Batson^[4] all proposed papers for crack arrest about such composites. Unfortunately, their works are restricted to the unidirectional short-fiber composites.

In this paper the theoretical analysis for the crack arrest are presented for both the unidirectional and random orientational short fibers in the matrix. Stress intensity factor and energy density factor are used to show the crack arresting effects.

2. ANALYSIS OF CRACK ARREST - CASE I

In the case of an aligned short-fiber composite subject to the remote uniform tensile

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stress σ_0^0 , we take the model shown in Figure 1 (a) where a short fiber is aligned in the loading direction and a penny-shaped crack located in the matrix is perpendicular to the loading direction. The model of Figure 1 (a) can be decomposed into two parts as Figure 1 (b) and (c): Figure 1 (b) represents the matrix while Figure 1 (c), the cutted fiber. In Figure 1 (b) the fiber is replaced by a set of self-equilibrant stress σ' . Again, Figure 1 (b) can be decomposed into Figure 1 (d) and (e). Figure 1 (d) denotes the case of matrix with crack but without reinforced fiber, and the matrix in Figure 1 (e) is subjected to stress set σ' which tends to close the crack from propagating.

Figure 1.

For the convenience of calculation we take Figure 2, where Figure 2 (a) is the normal section of Figure 1 (a). We decompose Figure 2 (a) into Figure 2 (b) and (c). There is no crack and no intensity factor K_I in the substructure Figure 2 (b), but there is a crack with internal pressure in the substructure Figure 2 (c). This internal pressure equals the magnitude but in opposite sign to the stress calculated from Figure 2 (b). Superimposing Figure 2 (b) and (c), we get the required traction free over the crack as in the structure of Figure 2 (a). Considering the fiber as a prolated spheroid inclusion, the distribution of stress σ in Figure 2 (b) can be got by Eshelby's^[5, 6] or Edwards's^[7] papers. We use the formulas under spheroidal coordinates derived by Edwards. After transformation [8] we obtain σ under the Cartesian coordinate system XYZ. Thus the intensity factor K_I of the substructure Figure 2 (c) can be given by the following formula [9]

Figure 2.

$$K_I = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^a \frac{\sigma r}{(\pi a)^{1.5}} \frac{\sqrt{1 - (r/a)^2}}{1 - 2(r/a)\cos\theta + (r/a)^2} d\theta dr \quad (1)$$

where a is the radius of the crack. Since $K_I = 0$ in the substructure Figure 2 (b), K_I given by Equation (1) is also the intensity factor of the structure Figure 2 (a). As in the structure of Figure 2 (a) without such a short fiber, it is well known the stress intensity factor

$$K'_I = 2\sigma_0 \sqrt{a/\pi} \quad (2)$$

we define

$$\varepsilon_1 = \frac{K'_I - K_I}{K'_I} \quad (3)$$

Thus, ε_1 gives the efficiency of crack arrest of the short fiber for case I. Proceeding as in the previous way, let shear stress τ^0 be used instead of σ^0 , we obtain

$$K_{II} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi a}} \int_{-a}^a \tau \sqrt{\frac{a+r}{a-r}} dr \quad (4)$$

where τ (instead of σ) can be calculated also by Edwards' formulas. For the case without fiber reinforcement

$$K'_{II} = \tau^0 \sqrt{\pi a} \quad (5)$$

Let

$$\varepsilon_2 = \frac{K'_{II} - K_{II}}{K'_{II}} \quad (6)$$

ε_2 denotes the efficiency of crack arrest of the short-fiber for case I but τ^0 instead of σ^0 .

3. ANALYSIS OF CRACK ARREST - CASE II

For random orientational short fibers in the matrix, we consider the model shown in Figure 3. Assume a short fiber is inclined to the crack plane XOY and uniform remote tensile stress σ^0 is applied in the direction of Z axis, the orientation of the fiber is defined by θ and φ . Take another Cartesian coordinate system OX'Y'Z' with Z' axis coincides the axis of the inclined short fiber, axis Y' can be taken to lie in the XOY plane in generality. The transformation matrix between two coordinates is given by

Figure 3.

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\theta & \sin\theta\cos\varphi & \sin\theta\sin\varphi \\ \sin\theta & -\cos\theta\cos\varphi & -\cos\theta\sin\varphi \\ 0 & \sin\varphi & -\cos\varphi \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

From Edwards' formulas we get the normal stress σ and shear stress $\tau (= \sqrt{\tau_{xx} + \tau_{xy}})$ upon the crack in Figure 3, then we get both K_I and K_{II} . Since K_I and K_{II} appear simultaneously, we use strain energy density factor $S^{[10]}$

$$S = a_{11} K_I^2 + 2a_{12} K_I K_{II} + a_{22} K_{II}^2 + a_{33} K_{III}^2 \quad (8)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} a_{11} &= (3 - 4\nu - \cos\alpha)(1 + \cos\alpha) / 16\pi G \cos\beta \\ a_{12} &= (2\sin\alpha)[\cos\alpha - (1 - 2\nu)] / 16\pi G \cos\beta \\ a_{22} &= [4(1 - \nu)(1 - \cos\alpha) \\ &\quad + (1 + \cos\alpha)(3\cos\alpha - 1)] / 16\pi G \cos\beta \\ a_{33} &= 1 / 4\pi G \cos\beta \end{aligned}$$

ν , G are the Poisson's ratio and shear modulus for matrix respectively, and α , β are shown in Figure 4. K_{III} is vanish in our problem. Let $\beta = 0$ we get S_{min} from $ds/d\alpha = 0$ and $d^2s/d\alpha^2 > 0$. For the case where fibers are in random orientations in the composite, assume there are fibers evenly distributed around the crack in different directions, we find the average S_{min} as \bar{S}

Figure 4.

$$\bar{S}' = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi \int_0^{\pi/2} S_{min} \sin\theta \, d\theta \quad (9)$$

For the case without fibers in Figure 3, only K_I' defined by Equation (2) is not vanished. From Equation (8), we get

$$\bar{S}' = \frac{1 - 2\nu}{\pi G} K_I'^2 \quad min \quad (10)$$

Then the crack arrest efficiency of random oriented short fibers is

$$\epsilon = \frac{S' - \bar{S}'_{min}}{S'} \quad (11)$$

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A circular crack in the concrete is centrally located between four adjacent wires, as shown in Figure 5 (a). The following data are chosen: $s = 1/d \rightarrow \infty$, $\nu = 0.35$, $V_f = 0$, $E = 3 \times 10^6$ psi, $E_f \rightarrow \infty$. The cracking stress (according to $K_{Ic} = 0.145 \text{ ksi} \sqrt{in}$ from [4]) vs wire spacing D are given in Figure 5 (b). Obviously there is good agreement of the present results with that of Romualdi and Batson ^[4].

Figure 5.

Other numerical results based on the present theory are as following: Three kinds of short fiber composites: short glass fiber reinforced epoxy, short steel fiber reinforced cement concrete and short nylon fiber reinforced asphalt mortar are considered. the material parameters used are shown in Table 1. The diameter of the crack is assumed to be 40 mm while fiber aspect ratio (l/d) be 10.

Table 1

	material 1		material 2		material 3	
	glass fiber	epoxy	steel fiber	cement concrete	nylon fiber	asphalt mortar
elastic modulus (N/m^2)	70.2×10^9	3.4×10^9	200×10^9	29.019×10^9	3.13×10^9	21.36×10^7
poisson's	0.25	0.3	0.3	0.17	0.4	0.3

Figure 6 and Figure 7 show the crack arrest efficiency of the aligned short-fiber composites, where L_u denotes the distance between the fiber and crack shown in Figure 1 (a). Figure 6 plots the crack arrest efficiencies ϵ_1 (%) vs L_u when the composite subjected to remote uniform tensile stress. And Figure 7 plots the crack arrest efficiencies ϵ_2 (%) vs L_u when composite subjected to remote uniform shear stress. It is seen from Figure 6 and 7 that the short fibers in composites can effectively prevent microcrack located in the matrix from propagating. And the shorter the distance between fiber and crack, the higher the the efficiency of crack arrest. Also it can be concluded that the crack arrest efficiency of short fibers while composites subjected to tensile stress is higher than that while composites subjected to shear stress. Figure 8 plots the crack arrest efficiency of random short fibers composites vs L_r . It follows from Figure 8 that random-short fibers can effectively prevent the crack extension.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

Figure 8.

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